

A Primer for Assessing Foundation Models for Earth Observation

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Abstract

Foundation Models (FMs) represent a transformative advancement for Earth Observation (EO), promising enhanced analysis and interpretation of complex spatial, spectral, and temporal data. However, selecting an appropriate FM for EO tasks remains challenging due to diverse model architectures, varied pretraining strategies, and nuanced evaluation metrics. Traditional benchmark-focused assessments are inadequate for capturing the full scope of EO-specific requirements, risking ineffective model selection. To address this, we introduce a structured assessment framework emphasizing four critical dimensions: pretraining data characteristics, tokenization processes, architectural choices, and downstream use case evaluations. This approach enables EO practitioners to systematically evaluate FMs based on data preprocessing rigor, token embedding strategies, model architecture suitability, and robustness in diverse real-world scenarios. Demonstrating the framework's practicality through comparative analysis of Prithvi-HLS models, our approach fosters informed, context-specific model integration, bridging the gap between FM developers and EO scientists and promoting responsible, effective FM utilization in EO workflows.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI) foundation models (FMs) are reshaping scientific workflows, especially in Earth observation (EO), where these models hold substantial promise. FMs are flexible tools that can be adapted to perform a range of tasks vital to applications such as climate and weather modeling, environmental monitoring, and disaster response. By capturing complex, high-dimensional data representations, they enable more efficient EO signal interpretation and support more precise, data-intensive analysis. Despite their potential, FMs remain underused in EO, particularly among remote sensing scientists who could benefit from integrating them into research workflows. A key challenge is choosing models suited to specific EO tasks. This challenge grows as the number of available FMs increases, each with different architectures, training data, and intended uses. Many EO researchers are unfamiliar with recent deep neural network architectures, making it difficult to evaluate models effectively. Hype around the newest or largest models often complicates the process, diverting focus from scientific relevance.

Model selection currently often depends on benchmark-based evaluations of downstream tasks. While this approach has proven effective in fields like natural language processing and computer vision, EO presents unique challenges. EO tasks involve signals with complex spatial, spectral, and temporal patterns such that a FM cannot be judged by downstream case performance metrics alone. Relying solely on use cases and benchmarks risks oversimplifying model performance and may lead to unsuitable choices.

For instance, a benchmark for image classification use case primarily based on object shape might rank a general-purpose model (FM A) above a specialized EO model (FM B). Just considering that benchmark may lead one to think that FM A is better for all EO image classification tasks. However, FM B might perform better in classification tasks requiring multispectral or temporal signals in the data.

Basing selection decisions on benchmark performance can limit the utility of FMs in research workflows. To make informed choices, EO practitioners need a systematic assessment strategy that considers how FMs are designed and trained. This primer introduces a structured framework for assessing FMs across four questions:

1. What were the characteristics of data used to pretrain the FM, including preprocessing?
2. How was the pretrained data modified before it was fed into the FM (tokenization process)?
3. What are the model architecture and design choices?
4. Do the use cases and evaluation benchmarks test that the model can differentiate signals in the data via relevance and representativeness?

The first two questions focus on data characteristics. Answering these questions helps determine what is possible for an optimal FM to learn from the data. The model architecture and additional design choices should further address how the model will learn from the data. The use cases with benchmarks are the proofs to show that an FM is performing as expected.

The framework should help bridge the gap between FM developers and EO scientists by providing a practical method for understanding and assessing models. Systematic evaluation across these dimensions reveals a model's strengths, limitations, and suitability for specific EO tasks. Without such assessment, model selection remains confusing and ineffective. Crucially, this framework does not rank or score models. Instead, it offers a diagnostic perspective to help EO researchers evaluate models based on their specific needs. Although this primer is focused primarily on optical remote sensing, the approach can be applied broadly. We demonstrate the framework's utility through a comparative case study of Prithvi-HLS v1.0 [2] and v2.0 [4], showing the design difference between the two models. This structured approach supports better evaluation practices and promotes responsible integration of FMs into EO workflows.

2. Background on Foundation Models

The term "foundation model" gained prominence in 2021, introduced by Stanford researchers[1] to describe models trained on broad datasets—typically using large-scale self-supervision—that can then be adapted to many downstream tasks. This definition of foundation models includes three main features: extensive training data, scalable self-supervision, and cross-task adaptability. A foundation model (FM) is usually a large neural network, often built on the transformer architecture and trained on large datasets through self-supervised learning. The dataset selected for pretraining should be useful for multiple downstream applications.

Traditional supervised deep learning models learn by minimizing a loss over labeled data, whereas FM generally learn via contrastive, autoregressive, or masked auto-encoding approaches. This approach enables the model to learn general-purpose representations that transfer well across various tasks. With millions or even billions of parameters, FMs can capture intricate patterns in high-dimensional data; this capacity allows them to generalize across tasks. Unlike traditional models—designed for narrow, task-specific objectives using labeled datasets—FMs learn from unlabeled data and require minimal fine-tuning for new tasks. This shift marks a fundamental change in AI workflows. The strength of FMs lies in their pretraining which exposes them to vast datasets and task-agnostic objectives, helping them extract reusable features. These pretrained models can transfer their learning and adapt to new tasks with limited labeled data. This transferability is a key benefit of utilizing FMs, significantly reducing computational and labeling demands during deployment. Different self-supervised learning strategies drive FM pretraining. For example, language models predict missing or next token, while vision models reconstruct masked image patches. These self-supervision strategies make efficient use of unlabeled data and avoid costly manual labeling.

Conceptually, an FM can be described by two functions:

- $z = F(x; \theta)$: The foundation model transforms raw input x into a latent representation z by a parametrized function F .
- $y = G(z) = G(F_{\theta}(x))$: A downstream task-specific head G maps this latent representation to an output y by learning a function G , which can be a subset or full set of parameter θ

During pretraining, the FM focuses on representation learning — uncovering meaningful latent features from raw data. For instance, a model trained to distinguish fruits in images may learn latent cues like shape or color, even if these attributes aren't explicit. These latent features underpin the model's usefulness during downstream tasks. This representation learning rests on the principle of manifold learning: high-dimensional real-world data tends to lie on lower-dimensional manifolds embedded in another lower-dimensional space. By learning these representations, FMs generalize more efficiently and require fewer labels for tasks like classification or clustering. The learned features — called embeddings — position "semantically" similar items close to one another in the latent space, enabling stronger generalization. Most

FMs use the transformer architecture, which was originally developed for natural language processing (NLP) but is now widely applied across domains. Its self-attention mechanism captures long-range dependencies and models contextual relationships across time, space and spectra — capabilities particularly valuable for EO tasks.

Figure 2A illustrates FM pretraining using a transformer architecture with an encoder-decoder setup. Input data is tokenized, with portions masked; the encoder learns the optimal latent representations when the decoder is able to effectively reconstruct the masked parts within a specified error threshold. This process facilitates general representation learning. In downstream applications, as shown in Figure 2B, only the encoder is retained. The decoder is replaced by a task-specific head, fine-tuned using labeled data for EO tasks like classification, segmentation or regression.

Recent efforts have produced large-scale FMs tailored to remote sensing (RS), signaling a shift from general-purpose vision models to EO-specific architectures. This development reflects the unique demands of EO imagery — such as multispectral channels, varying spatial resolutions, and irregular temporal sampling — that generic models often fail to handle effectively. RS-dedicated FMs, designed with these characteristics in mind, have shown improved performance on EO tasks, validating their practical value and domain relevance.

Figure 1. Conceptual representation of a foundation model.

The foundation model F transforms raw input x into a latent representation z , capturing abstract features through self-supervised pretraining. A task-specific head H then maps z to an output y , enabling adaptation for classification application. Similarly, a task-specific head G then maps z to an output y , enabling adaptation for prediction application. This two-stage process — representation learning followed by task-specific fine-tuning — illustrates the generalization and flexibility of foundation models.

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} \mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_{\text{target}}} [\mathcal{L}_{\text{task}} (f_{\theta}(x), y)]$$

Where f_{θ} is the pretrained model, x and y are the input images and target labels. We can decouple the block of finetuning by:

$$f_{\theta}(x) = h_{\phi} (g_{\theta'}(x))$$

Where $g_{\theta'}$ is the frozen or finetuned backbone, and h_{ϕ} is the task-specific head.

Figure 2. Training and adaptation of transformer-based foundation models.

(A) During pre training, input data is tokenized and partially masked. The encoder learns to represent the input in a latent space, and the decoder reconstructs the masked content. This masked reconstruction task drives the model to learn generalized, transferable features.

(B) For downstream EO tasks, the decoder is discarded. The encoder is retained and paired with a new, task-specific head fine-tuned on labeled data (e.g., for segmentation or classification), enabling efficient adaptation to EO applications.

3. Informing the Foundation Model (FM): Science First Principles for Optical Remote Sensing

While FMs for EO can be pre trained using various data types including Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) and thermal imagery, this primer focuses on optical remote sensing. Accordingly, this section reviews the foundational principles from optical remote sensing as those described in *Jensen's Remote Sensing of the Environment [3]*. These principles should guide the design of geospatial AI FMs.

In optical remote sensing, the core physical measurement is radiance, described by the equation:

$$L = f(W, s(x, y, z), t, \theta, \omega)$$

Here, radiance L depends on spectral characteristics W , spatial location $s(x,y,z)$, time t , angular dependencies θ , and sensor-specific parameters ω . A well-designed geospatial FM should explicitly learn and model these variables as signals to accurately interpret optical EO data.

3.1 Spatial Information

Radiance is observed at precise spatial coordinates with defined resolution and extent. The FM should not only learn isolated measurements but also recognize spatial relationships and patterns. For instance, it must distinguish between abrupt transitions typical in urban areas and the gradual shifts seen in natural landscapes. Modeling these contexts improves performance in many spatial analysis tasks.

3.2 Spectral Information

Spectral information W includes surface/atmospheric properties across multiple wavelengths. For a given location, spectral bands may reveal distinct characteristics of the surface properties, often called spectral signatures. The bands can be analyzed in combination to infer new information. For example, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) uses red and Near Infrared (NIR) bands to indicate vegetation health. The FM should model individual band values and the inter-band relationships that capture meaningful spectral signatures. Incorporating multispectral data $[W1(x,y), W2(x,y), \dots, Wn(x,y)]$ through spectral embeddings allows the model to efficiently learn these dependencies.

3.3 Temporal Information

While a single measurement represents a snapshot in time, modeling temporal variation is important for monitoring trends. Temporal variation t in radiance captures seasonal cycles, growth stages, and anomalies such as droughts or floods. As such, FMs should process EO data as a time series of measurement $[L(t1), L(t2), \dots, L(tn)]$. The models should include temporal encodings, like day-of-year, to learn both periodic and anomalous behaviors. For datasets such as Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 (HLS) with revisit cycles on the order of days, diurnal resolution may be unnecessary. Still, incorporating metadata about time and date of the measurement can help the model detect relevant trends and temporal dynamics.

3.4 Location Information

Geographic location (x,y) information introduces another context that influences observed radiance. For example, coastal and inland areas often exhibit distinct reflectance patterns, just as elevation affects snow or vegetation prevalence. FMs should embed geographic priors using latitude and longitude encodings to learn regional dependencies. These encodings help generalize across diverse environments by integrating location-specific influences directly into model representations.

4. Assessment Framework

To evaluate whether a FM suits specific EO tasks, we propose a structured assessment along four dimensions. Each dimension looks at what an FM learns during pretraining and how learning outcomes influence its performance and relevance for specific EO tasks. This approach can help EO practitioners evaluate FMs critically and thoroughly.

Figure 3: Mapping of the proposed four-dimensional assessment framework onto the pretraining and fine-tuning process of Foundation Models (FMs) for Earth Observation (EO).

4.1 Data Used for Pretraining

A foundation model's performance depends heavily on the characteristics of its pretraining data. In remote sensing, these characteristics are based on instrument characteristics such as resolution, geographic and temporal coverage, and spectral composition, as well as preprocessing steps. These characteristics dictate what the model can learn from the data.

1. Data Source

Pretraining data should come from authoritative sources, such as government agencies or international science missions, which follow rigorous calibration and validation protocols. Trusted datasets minimize risks from radiometric errors, geo-registration issues, or sensor inconsistencies. Using dependable pretraining data reduces uncertainty and supports reliable model development.

2. Spatial Resolution

Spatial resolution determines the smallest features a model can recognize. High-resolution data (e.g., 10 m Sentinel-2) reveals finer spatial patterns; low-resolution data (e.g., 30 m Landsat) may blur or miss small-scale details. Matching resolution to the task is critical. For instance, field-level crop classification typically requires resolution finer than 30 m. As a rule of thumb, spatial resolution should be less than half the size of the smallest target feature [3].

3. Preprocessing

Preprocessing steps convert raw satellite data from a sensor into usable scientific inputs. Without proper preprocessing such as calibrations, models may learn spurious signals from artifacts. Some examples of preprocessing steps common in optical remote sensing are atmospheric correction, bidirectional reflectance distribution function (BRDF) adjustment, geometric correction and bandpass adjustment. Atmospheric correction removes atmospheric distortions like aerosol scattering or water vapor absorption. For example, the HLS pipeline applies LaSRC algorithms to convert top of the atmosphere (TOA) reflectance into surface reflectance. This ensures consistency across dates and scenes. Similarly, BRDF adjustment corrects for variations in sun-sensor geometry using relevant models. It ensures that the same surface does not exhibit false radiometric variation due to changing angles. Geometric correction or projection aligns images from different sensors or dates onto a common grid. Misalignment can lead to spatial noise and confuse the model (e.g., aligning water bodies with farmland). Finally, bandpass adjustment normalizes spectral band differences between optical sensors, like Landsat and Sentinel-2. Without this adjustment, the model may develop inconsistent responses to similar inputs.

4. Geographic Coverage

The broader the spatial coverage, the more generalizable the model. Pretraining only in one region (e.g., the U.S.) limits performance in different environments (e.g., tropics or mountains). Global datasets promote robustness but require diverse and balanced sampling strategies.

5. Spectral Information

The number and types of spectral bands define which biophysical phenomena the model can detect. NIR bands support vegetation indices like NDVI, while short wave infrared (SWIR) bands help with moisture estimation and burn detection. Models trained without critical bands often struggle in tasks relying on those features. Higher spectral resolution also improves class separation — for example, distinguishing wetlands from grasslands.

6. Temporal Resolution

Temporal resolution refers to how often a sensor revisits a location. High revisit rates (e.g., daily) allow monitoring of dynamic events like floods. Lower frequencies are more suited to long-term change detection. Matching the revisit cycle to the application is essential.

7. Temporal Coverage

Temporal coverage captures the historical range of training data. Single-year datasets often fail under unusual conditions or evolving regimes. Multi-year coverage exposes the model to inter-annual variability, improving long-term robustness.

8. Additional Preprocessing

Beyond core steps, additional preprocessing — such as cloud masking, noise filtering, and missing data imputation — improves data quality. Removing cloudy scenes or interpolating gaps enhances temporal consistency, which is especially vital for optical sensors.

9. Sampling Strategy

Data is typically sampled to pretrain the FM because datasets contain much redundant information. Effective sampling ensures both diversity and balance. Random sampling can overrepresent dominant classes and miss rare ones. Stratified or regime-based approaches improve representation across land cover types, climates, and biomes. However, the sampling strategy must be carefully managed to avoid introducing new biases.

10. Data Augmentation

Augmentation increases data diversity and model robustness. Techniques like flipping, rotation, and cropping expand the training set. Including auxiliary data — such as digital elevation models — adds contextual information, improving performance in complex terrains and underrepresented regions.

Table 1. Comparing Prithvi v1.0 and v2.0 foundation models along the data dimension.

	Prithvi - HLS v1.0	Prithvi - HLS v2.0
Data Product(s)	Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 (HLS) - S30, L30 (Regional)	Harmonized Landsat and Sentinel-2 (HLS) - S30, L30 (Global)
Spatial Resolution	30 m	30 m
Preprocessing to Create	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LaSRC atmospheric correction • BRDF normalization • Geometric alignment • Bandpass adjustment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LaSRC atmospheric correction • BRDF normalization • Geometric alignment • Bandpass adjustment
Spatial Coverage Used	Contiguous U.S. only (e.g., 48 states)	World-wide (2014–2023)
Spectral Information	Six spectral bands (blue, green, red, NIR, SWIR1, SWIR2)	Six spectral bands (blue, green, red, NIR, SWIR1, SWIR2)
Temporal Coverage Used	Data from 2017 only	Data from 2014–2023 (multi-year variability)
Additional Preprocessing	Filter out missing/cloudy data	Filter out missing/cloudy data; remove problematic tiles (e.g., Greenland ice)

Sampling Approach	Stratified sampling over 20 climate regions in the U.S.	Combining land-use classes & ecoregions; removing homogeneous sea/desert
Data Augmentation	Random crops, flips	Random crops, flips

4.2 Tokenization Process

Tokens are the fundamental input units for foundation models. In language models, they represent words or subwords; in Earth observation, tokens typically originate from dividing images into non-overlapping patches. These patches reduce computational complexity — especially for high-resolution imagery — while retaining essential spatial structure. In EO, tokens can extend beyond spatial patches to include spectral and temporal dimensions, forming multidimensional arrays that encode rich environmental signals.

1. Token Size

Token size determines how large image regions (e.g., 224×224 pixels) are subdivided into smaller patches (e.g., 16×16 or 14×14 pixels). Coarser patches reduce the number of tokens and ease memory demands, but they risk omitting smaller features like roads or tree crowns. Finer patch size preserves detail but increases computational load. For example, a 16×16 patch size on a 224×224 image produces about 14×14 tokens, while a 14×14 patch size yields ~16×16 tokens, offering more spatial granularity at higher computational cost. The appropriate choice depends on the application: field-scale tasks like crop classification may tolerate larger patches, while fine-scale delineation tasks benefit from smaller ones.

2. Spectral Token Grouping

In multispectral or hyperspectral data, bands can be processed individually or grouped into broader spectral categories. Grouping (e.g., blue + green) reduces input dimensionality and memory use but may blur critical spectral distinctions. Keeping bands separate preserves spectral fidelity, allowing models to learn subtle patterns — for instance, using SWIR for burn scars or NIR for vegetation health. The trade-off between efficiency and precision should align with the task. Burn severity mapping, for example, may demand separate treatment of NIR and SWIR to avoid performance loss.

3. 3D Patch Structure: Time, Space, and Spectral Dimensions

Many EO FMs use 3D tokens that integrate time, spatial dimensions, and spectral bands. Each token forms a spatiotemporal cube—such as $4 \times 16 \times 16 \times 6$, representing four time steps, spatial patches, and six spectral bands. This structure allows the model to learn joint temporal, spatial, and spectral patterns. These embeddings support complex EO tasks, such as change detection, phenological modeling, and material classification, but increase memory requirements. Designers often adjust the number of time steps or patch sizes to meet hardware constraints. The temporal information modeled in the 3D patch structure is important and affects what the FM learns.

4. Temporal Information Design

The time dimension in the 3D patch structure limits what a model can learn. The temporal input — both its duration and frequency — determines a model’s ability to capture dynamic changes. Short intervals (e.g., 10 days) detect rapid events like flooding or harvesting, while longer intervals (1–6 months) suit tasks like crop development or forest regrowth. The temporal cadence learned by the model must align with the application. An FM trained on closely spaced acquisitions may detect short-term anomalies well, but it may fail to capture long-term trends if the intervals are too brief. Choosing the wrong sequence length or spacing can impact model performance.

5. Positional Encoding

Since models process image patches independently, positional encodings restore structural relationships across space and time. Without this encoding, the model cannot infer adjacency or relative positioning, which limits its ability to reconstruct coherent scenes. Positional cues are essential for transformers handling EO imagery.

Table 2. Comparing Prithvi v1.0 and v2.0 foundation models along token structure and embedding dimensions.

		Prithvi v1.0	Prithvi v2.0
Spatial Size	Token	16×16 patches on 224×224 input → ~14×14 tokens	14×14 patch size on 224×224 input → ~16×16 tokens (higher model capacity, more detail)
Spectral Grouping	Token	None (each of 6 bands is treated as a distinct channel)	None (keeps each band separate for maximum spectral fidelity)

3D Patch Embedding	(1 × 16 × 16 × 6) 1 time-step only	(4 × 16 × 16 × 6) sequences of 4 time steps spaced by 1–6 months
Temporal Information	3 consecutive acquisitions (each ~10 days apart) → short cycle	4 acquisitions spaced up to 6 months (capturing partial seasonal to multi-month changes)
Positional Encoding	3D positional embedding - 1D positional encodings for height, width, and time, and then combine the individual encodings into a single, 3D positional encoding	3D positional embedding - 1D positional encodings for height, width, and time, and then combine the individual encodings into a single, 3D positional encoding

4.3 Architecture

1. Base Architecture (ViT, Swin, etc.)

Most EO foundation models use Vision Transformers (ViTs) or their variants as core architectures, adapted to handle geospatial data. These models convert satellite imagery — whether single-date or multi-temporal — into latent feature representations, which feed into task-specific heads for classification, segmentation, or regression during fine-tuning. Standard ViTs rely on global self-attention, allowing each token to interact with every other token. This mechanism captures long-range spatial, spectral, and temporal dependencies, enabling the model to learn broad patterns such as regional phenology or forest disturbance. However, the computational cost rises significantly with input size or sequence length.

To balance efficiency and capacity, designers often adjust patch embedding sizes or input dimensions. While global attention excels in recognizing large-scale patterns, it may falter on tasks needing local precision, like road extraction or tree detection. Localized attention models, such as Swin Transformers or ViT-Hybrid variants, address this limitation by restricting each token’s attention to a surrounding window. These architectures scale better with input size and perform best in fine-grained tasks like urban segmentation or boundary delineation. To retain broader context, they may use strategies like shifted windows or hierarchical attention.

Choosing the right architecture directly affects model performance, memory use, and fine-tuning effort. Global-attention models suit broad-scale tasks like land cover mapping; localized models perform better in object-level analyses.

2. Parameter Size

Parameter size reflects the number of trainable weights, ranging from tens of millions to over a billion. These include weights in attention layers, normalization, and feedforward networks. Larger models can capture subtle variations in spatial, spectral, and temporal data, such as seasonal cycles or sensor inconsistencies, and often generalize better across regions and time.

For instance, Prithvi-HLS v2.0, with over 600 million parameters, demonstrates strong generalization across diverse EO settings. Large models also fine tune more effectively on small datasets, a common scenario in remote sensing. However, they demand more training resources, increase inference time, and may overfit if pretrained on limited data. Smaller models are easier to deploy and are often preferred during early experimentation or in resource-constrained environments.

3. Pretext Training (Self-Supervised Strategy)

Self-supervised pretext tasks enable FMs to learn from unlabeled data, extracting transferable features across spatial, spectral, and temporal domains. Key strategies include masked autoencoding (MAE), next token prediction, and contrastive learning. MAE strategy randomly masks parts of the input — spatial, spectral, or temporal — and trains the model to reconstruct them. The dimension masked influences the model's focus; spatial masking enhances localization, spectral masking builds inter-spectral band understanding, and temporal masking captures change dynamics. In the next token prediction strategy, the model is given a sequence of inputs. The model predicts the next time step. This supports learning of event progression and seasonality, aiding short-term forecasting and imputation. In contrastive learning, the model is encouraged to group similar scenes and separate dissimilar ones in embedding space. This approach is valuable for tasks like land use classification and change detection where subtle differences matter. Each pretext task introduces an inductive bias; reconstruction promotes contextual understanding, forecasting strengthens temporal reasoning, and contrastive methods improve feature discrimination.

4. Domain Knowledge Incorporation

Some models integrate physical or geophysical principles into their architecture or training objectives. For example, EO models may include climatology-aware terms in their loss functions, penalizing deviations from historical norms. Prithvi Weather x Climate (WxC) incorporates such terms to enhance stability and realism. Embedding domain constraints improves model robustness, especially under distribution shifts or rare conditions. However, these constraints may limit flexibility or performance in unfamiliar scenarios. Balancing physics-based priors with data-driven learning remains an active research area in geospatial AI.

Additional information beyond the data can also be used to enhance a model’s contextual understanding. For example, metadata about satellite observations can be encoded for location and time. Location encoding (latitude and longitude) grounds the model in geographic context. Reflectance varies by region — tropics, temperate zones, and polar areas differ significantly. Adding geolocation helps the FM distinguish, for example, snow-covered forests from clouds based on latitude. Similarly, time encoding (e.g., day-of-year or year) captures phenological patterns and seasonal cycles. These can be encoded as cyclical functions (sine/cosine) or categorical tokens. Time-aware inputs improve performance in seasonal monitoring, crop phenology, and drought detection.

5. Loss Function

Loss functions guide model learning by quantifying prediction errors. For reconstruction tasks like MAE, mean squared error (MSE) is commonly used; it penalizes large deviations, encouraging precise outputs. However, MSE may overlook subtle but important differences in EO applications. Custom loss designs can also be used to prioritize specific dimensions. Temporal loss penalizes inconsistency across time steps, preserving seasonal continuity and supporting phenological analysis. Similarly, spectral consistency loss enforces realistic spectral relationships, avoiding physically implausible predictions like high NIR reflectance from water. Composite or domain-specific losses align model objectives with EO applications, improving performance in time-series analysis, sensor harmonization, and other science-driven tasks.

Table 3. Comparing Prithvi v1.0 and v2.0 foundation models along the architecture dimension

	Prithvi v1.0	Prithvi v2.0
Base Architecture	ViT (vision transformer)	ViT (with optional lat/lon/time metadata in the token embeddings)
Parameter Size	~100M parameters	~300M / 600M / 1B (larger capacity, more complex spatiotemporal relationships)
Pretext Training	Masked autoencoder (MAE) with random spatial masking	Masked autoencoder (MAE) with random spatiotemporal masking (4×16×16×6 patches)

EO Domain Knowledge	None explicitly	None explicit, but lat/lon/day-of-year encodings incorporate geographical/time context
(Location & Time Encoding)	None: model doesn't embed lat/lon or day-of-year	Embeds lat/lon, plus a cyclical day-of-year for each sample to track seasonal changes
Loss Function	MSE on 1 time-step \times $16 \times 16 \times 6$ input (reconstructing masked patches)	MSE on 4 time-steps \times $16 \times 16 \times 6$ input (reconstructing masked patches across space, time, bands)

4.4 Assessment of Use Cases

Foundation models for Earth observation are typically evaluated using benchmarked use cases paired with training datasets. These use cases span various EO applications such as flood mapping, crop classification, burn scar segmentation, and biomass estimation. Performance is often gauged by comparing FM outputs against established baselines, including conventional machine learning/deep learning models or other FMs on similar tasks.

However, evaluating utility demands more than numerical performance metrics. The design and scope of use cases also need scrutiny, especially regarding task diversity, generalization, and real-world robustness.

1. Task Diversity

A strong evaluation framework should cover a wide range of task types including classification, segmentation, regression, detection, and inpainting. EO FMs are rarely tailored to a single function; practitioners may fine-tune the same model across applications, from vegetation monitoring to disaster response. Evaluating across varied task structures (e.g., pixel-level segmentation vs. object-level detection) offers a clearer view of the model's adaptability. Task diversity also acts as a proxy for generalization. A model that performs well across several task categories is more likely to adapt to new or unforeseen use cases. For instance, a model excelling at both burn area segmentation and gross primary productivity (GPP) estimation demonstrates greater versatility and operational value.

2. Use Case Completeness

Effective assessment extends beyond task accuracy; it evaluates whether the FM truly handles real-world variability and complexity. This includes spatial and temporal generalization, class and value coverage, and robustness to data quality issues.

A well-designed FM should retain performance when applied to new regions or time periods. EO applications often operate across continents and years. A model fine-tuned on one region or season may fail in different environmental conditions, such as during monsoon years or wildfire seasons. Evaluation should include out-of-distribution testing that spans both space and time.

The FM must also capture the full range of classes or values relevant to the task. In classification, this means handling both dominant and rare classes, such as wetlands or urban peripheries. In regression, it requires modeling edge cases, including extreme biomass values. Assessments should quantify whether rare or extreme cases are represented in the data and whether the model handles them effectively.

Satellite imagery often suffers from noise, clouds, missing data, or shadows. FMs must demonstrate resilience under these real-world imperfections. A reliable model should degrade gracefully, maintaining plausible outputs despite corrupted or partial inputs. For example, Prithvi v1.0 showed promising results in controlled evaluations for burn scar detection. However, when applied to real HLS imagery with cloud cover, edge shadows, and residual artifacts, the model produced a high rate of false positives. This exposed gaps in the evaluation data and highlighted the need for test cases that better reflect actual data quality issues.

Robust use case design must include corrupted inputs and test how well the FM copes with them. Operational viability depends not just on peak accuracy, but on consistent performance under less-than-ideal conditions.

Table 4: Comparing Prithvi v1.0 and v2.0 foundation models along the assessment of use cases dimension. The models are compared on task diversity alone. Assessing completeness of each use case has not yet been conducted.

	Prithvi v1.0	Prithvi v2.0
Task Diversity	<p>Inpainting - multi-temporal cloud gap imputation</p> <p>Semantic segmentation - flood mapping, fire-scar segmentation, multi-temporal crop segmentation</p>	<p>Semantic segmentation - flood mapping, wild scar segmentation, burn intensity mapping, landslide detection, multi-temporal crop segmentation</p> <p>Classification - multi-temporal land cover and crop classification</p>

		Regression/Prediction - above ground biomass estimation, estimation of GPP
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5. Summary

Foundation models are reshaping Earth observation by offering scalable, generalizable solutions across tasks such as land cover mapping, flood detection, and environmental monitoring. Yet, their adoption remains challenging — especially for domain scientists unfamiliar with deep learning architecture, model design, and evaluation nuances. Current evaluation methods, which focus primarily on benchmark scores for selected use cases, often fall short in guiding FM selection for EO applications. To close this gap, this primer introduces a structured, science-driven assessment framework. Designed with EO practitioners in mind, the framework supports informed, context-aware evaluation of FMs, particularly in optical remote sensing. It centers on key EO signal dimensions — spatial, spectral, temporal, and geographic — and emphasizes how these should guide both FM selection and evaluation.

The framework outlines four core dimensions:

Pretraining data characteristics: including data source reliability, spatial and temporal resolution, preprocessing rigor, and geographic coverage.

Tokenization process: covering patch size and 3D patch structures, especially the temporal dimension.

Model architecture and design: assessing backbone design (e.g., ViT variants), parameter size, pretext training strategies, and loss functions.

Downstream use case evaluation: focusing on task diversity, completeness, and resilience under data quality constraints.

Rather than ranking models, the framework helps practitioners assess whether a given FM fits their specific task requirements and operational context. This diagnostic approach fosters transparency and scientific grounding in model selection. A comparison between Prithvi HLS v1.0 and v2.0 illustrates the framework in action. It shows how design shifts — such as broader spatial coverage, richer temporal modeling, and increased model capacity — translate into measurable performance gains.

Ultimately, this framework bridges the gap between FM developers and EO scientists. By doing so, it supports responsible, effective integration of foundation models into research and real-world EO workflows.

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7. Suggested Reading

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